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From Motherhood to Nationhood: A Historicist Re-reading of Anisul Hoque's *Maa*

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***Abstract:** This paper studies Anisul Hoque's *Maa* to trace the route to the evolution of a mother who transcends subjective boundary and emerges as an incarnation of nationhood to sustain the spirit of the Liberation War of Bangladesh in 1971 and enlivens the emancipatory prospects even after her death. As a narrative to rewrite a nation's history with newer perspectives, the author chooses a female protagonist in the background of the Liberation War, and with an ethnographic approach, collects data to conform to historical realities and develop the fiction to craft a mother-figure who with her self-determinism, sacrifice, nurturing agency and resistance distinguishes herself. Safia Begum, as an individual, transcends and merges with the synchronous and diachronous national discourses aligning her own self with collective motherhood. With insights from nationalist literature, identity, spatial theory and risk space, this paper seeks to demonstrate how Hoque projects a character which turns into a representative motherhood metaphorically aligning with the gradual formation process of the nationhood based on the Liberation War of Bangladesh.*

Keywords: Nationhood, Motherhood, Historicity, Determinism, Narrative

Research Questions

The paper is around the character of a mother and her sustaining image as a collective subjectivity, and so concentrates on the following questions:

- a. What does it mean to be suppressed in adversity for a female figure within a patriarchal power-structure?
- b. How does Anisul Hoque map the alleged complicity between self-determinism and nationhood, mythopoetically projected through the gradual development of the character of Safia Begum?

Research Objectives

The researchers aim to explore the dimensions of a mother who from being a subjective self emerges as an objective self, representing collective motherhood which unequivocally works as a potent drive behind the birth and consistent formation of a political desirability and leads a nation to freedom from a “liminal, barely human existence” (Gandhi 111). Borrowing the framework from postcolonial theories of nation and narration, this paper will demonstrate how the author addresses the web of nationhood through the synchronous and diachronous development of the character of Safia Begum.

Literature Review

On the Liberation War of Bangladesh, innumerable literary works, painting, songs and art work have been created, but amongst all, to Ramendu Majumdar, one of the leading intellectuals of the country, “only two books have become classic, *Ekattorer Dinguli* by Jahanara Imam and *Maa* by Anisul Hoque”. Martyr-mother Jahanara Imam incorporates her experiences pertinent to the Liberation War of Bangladesh in 1971. This autobiography is dedicated to the narrative of her son Shafi Imam Rumi’s fight against Pakistani army in Dhaka and other regions. It also reflects

on Sharif Imam, her husband's death during the Liberation War. On the other, Anisul Hoque depicts the struggle of Safia Begum whose son Azad, a guerrilla fighter of the Liberation War disappeared from the custody of the Pakistani army, and she lives on his recollection and in course of the narrative of the novel, her struggle for survival turns metaphorical with the vicissitudes in the journey of nationhood of Bangladesh.

Basha and Kumar investigate the culture of resistance among the people of Bangladesh and find a long history of this culture in Hoque who “explores the culture of resistance in many contexts and actions” (267). In *Freedom's Mother* (English translation of *Maa*), they find the reflection of the continuation of the resistance through the freedom fighters along with Azad and Safia Begum who were instrumental in sustaining the spirit of the Bengalis. Khan reads the novel as a treatment of the tragedy of the Liberation War of Bangladesh as well as the story of Safia Begum's uncompromising personality. To her, Hoque has been poetic in his rendition with a circular structure of the novel beginning and ending with the funeral of Safia Begum and stresses the historical accuracy. The novel, thus, according to her, “is a history of the human cost of war seen through the eyes of a mother” (8). Das finds Hoque's attempt one among others to reconstruct the narratives on the seminal epic war of Bangladesh after long silence regarding the trauma of the war, and the author “has chanced upon the haunting tale” of a mother and develops the narrative on the brutality of the Pakistani army during the war (10). Chakravorty considers the novel as “sensitively crafted” and weaved “in and out of a patchwork of memories” of the freedom fighters and a mother who have gone through trials and tribulations (18). To her, “A long way from the rich man's wife in a mansion where swans glided among fountains, Safia merges here with the thousands of mothers denied the pitying kindness of closure - in Kashmir and the Northeast, perhaps, in Sri Lanka and the Middle East, in villages and towns and islands, unknown and unsung in history” (18). To Nahid Khan, it is “a literary reconstruction of history” with real names and facts about people, place and period.

He finds in this narrative a tribute to all the sacrificing mothers by telling “a story of love, courage, sacrifice, resentment, commitment, sadness, tears and triumph”. Parvin locates the novel in the patriarchal structure where the women’s roles are mostly undermined, but this text represents the “moral and ideological support” the freedom fighters got from the women as well as the “war mothers’ anxiety, dilemma” and sacrifice (113). The novel is studied by Basha and Prem Raj as an attempt to construct identity through “resistance, regeneration or reconstruction of traditional forms of life” (95). In the novel, the mother manifests her self-respect and heroic nature that “paved the way for bringing new consciousness among the people of Bangladesh” ushering the democratic sense (98). Das makes an extensive study on the fictions written about the Liberation War and traces the silences of war narratives, limits of nationalist creative works, testimony to the war crimes through ‘Birangona’ narratives and the existence of the muted. In her study, she stresses how the nationalist fictions sensitize us, and Hoque’s novel “casts the suffering mother of a guerrilla and a martyr as a part of nationalistic lore” and “articulate[s] the narratives and tongues buried at the sites of national mythmaking” (192). The narrative falls short as a novel to Aiyar, and the author has sketched the characters and the storyline ensuring “a touching authenticity to the dialogues and the characters”. To him, it “is the story of the mothers, sisters and wives who saw their lives being taken from them even as they suppressed their personal fears of the worst in the larger cause of the motherland”.

The researchers pay their attention on Hoque’s sincere attempt to capture the seminal War of the Liberation of 1971, and the portrayal of the mother’s determination and sacrifices during her lifetime against the backdrop of the patriarchal structure. There is hardly any focus on the nationalist aspect of the character of Safia Begum who has emerged as a mother analogous with the motherland itself. This study concentrates on the course of action a mother who symbolizes the gradual emergence of the Bangladesh as a nation-state.

Hoque's Archaeology of the Nationalist Project

Parallelism between fact and fiction runs through the narrative of the novel. Though Anisul Hoque incorporates historical documents into the narrative of this novel, and though, for this reason, many call it a docu-fiction, Hoque's delicate power of intertextualizing fact with fiction, the novel transcends its narrow status of being a historical text. As a part of the project of re-creating an ordinary female figure out of oblivion, Hoque has adopted an archaeological approach, conducted in-depth interviews of those who had close relation with Safia Begum and Azad and made case study and FGD as well as carried out archival research for crafting the character of the protagonist. Along with the individual spaces of Safia Begum, Hoque has set the narrative to cover wider angles encompassing the major historical juncture of Bangladesh, including the Mass Movement of 1969, the election of 1970 and specially the epic War of Independence in 1971. Thus, the narrative has come to connect individual with the national merging the micro with macro which in turn has transformed the narrative into an all-covering melting pot to contain the whole of Bangladesh as much as possible, and the mother Safia Begum and the country have become interchangeable or mutually complementary. Her stance on the face of the critical juncture regarding her son Azad's custody in Ramana Thana constantly and potently questions the dominant system of thought and ethics, and this integrity regarding her characteristic strictness is essential for gaining freedom. In this connection, Salman Rushdie's view, in this connection, appears very relevant:

Liberty relies on the constant interrogation of any critical system's first principles. When one is not allowed to question the first principles of the dominant system of thought, and when the penalties for doing so are dire, one finds oneself trapped in a tyranny. (234)

Safia Begum's stance interprets a tremendous interrogation of the oppressive colonial hegemony which leads her son Azad to be

trapped in tyranny and oppression. But her indomitable subjectivity echoes the self of the country which is badly in need of freedom and posing all possible sorts of resistance against political enslavement.

Merging Individual and National Life

Safia Begum's consistent process of becoming the dignified mother of martyred Azad is not a neat homogeneous construction as she recklessly wrestles in the space between feudalism and capitalism. The rigor that she carries with her emanates from feudal disposition and on the other hand, her location in the society as a wife of Yunus Chowdhury and a woman with a capitalist paternal background, she belongs to the bourgeoisie of the capitalist economic framework. The process of her being a metaphor of the struggle of the people of Bangladesh for liberty in 1971 aptly interprets the typical ambivalence and anxiety emerging out of the existential crisis of the nation. After the disappearance of Azad from the custody of the Pakistani police, Safia Begum avowedly deserts all sorts of comfort of her life. She sleeps on the floor and eats no rice, only *ruti* (bread) and on the other hand, she possesses a huge mass of gold she preserved for Azad's prospective wife and the real estate that she owns is quite dichotomous. Feudal practice of life on the one hand, and on the other, her bourgeois background creates an ambivalence which is a typical characteristic of a state. Even today after 53 years of liberty Bangladesh is ambivalent regarding a distinct course of nature or identity in terms of its political and economic realities.

Even her alienation from the society interprets the bureaucratic decorum of re-creating self-voice or self-conversation and in such state an individual does not abandon his/her desire to be segregated from the community. In this connection, Stephen Greenblatt sounds very relevant when he proclaims:

It was true that I could hear only my own voice, but my own voice was the voice of the dead, for the dead had

contrived to leave textual traces of themselves, and those traces make themselves heard in the voices of the living. Many of the traces have little resonance, though everyone, even the most trivial or tedious, contains some fragment of lost life; others seem uncannily full of the will to be heard. (496)

Safia Begum's one of the ultimate desires that she opens up to Zayed, her sister's son, that she should have an epitaph with the inscription '*Shaheed Azader Maa*' (Mother of martyred Azad) interprets her "will to be heard" (14). This determined position consciously chosen is not confined only to her motherly attachment to the son; it rather unveils her attitude to the martyred whom she values more than any other identity can confer. This positionality proves the invaluable prowess and price of those who sacrifice lives for the country, and the mother is generous in acknowledging their worth in relation to the liberation which promises a society without discrimination and so "the coolie leader Rashid and the Editor of *Weekly Bichitra* Shahadat Choudhury share the same cigarette" (16). This heterogeneity of a people contests the problematizing concept of the nation especially which emerged after the Second World War. Even the concept of the membership of an individual provokes insoluble ambiguity because, "[A] single individual in the developed world is likely to be a member (willingly or unwillingly) of one state, but membership of nation, people or culture may in each case be contested or multiple" (Hawthorn 229). The contrapuntal juxtaposition of the characters of Chowdhury and Safia Begum can be interpreted as the problematic development of the concept of the nation-state. Yunus Chowdhury and Safia Begum are the members of the same state but they do not belong to the same nation because nationhood is basically mental, not geographical.

Ironically several nations may exist in a single state because nationhood splits up in consequence of the ambivalence emanating out of a divide mind. Yunus Chowdhury's attachment with the then Pakistani elites defines his Pakistani nationhood, even after

the birth of Bangladesh which Safia Begum wholly aligns with her own entity. Thus, the gradual process of transformation of her personal life is metaphorically concomitant with the Liberation War of Bangladesh, and she holds on to her position securing dignity kicking away lavishness of wealth and insurance of security. The rigorous personal battle protesting against the second marriage of her millionaire husband continues till the end equating her struggle with the nation in the fight for real emancipation. Safia Begum's protest explicates her desire to develop her own self of subjectivity. Her protest itself is a language, and it is undeniable that language is needed for the construction of selfhood or subjectivity and when this selfhood apprehends a probable threat to its existence, it uses language to reclaim its desired object, that is, self which "... is not a single, consistent entity, but a divided or multiple 'self' located within and constructed by its many different discourses" (Barker 99). 'Self' appears when the individual is deprived out of the absolute possession of his or her desired object by a figure of authority. In this connection, Yunus Chowdhury's second marriage manifests the masculine authority which poses a threat to the 'self' of Safia Begum as an independent entity and hence, her protest and her ultimate decision of leaving her husband and never seeing his face in her lifetime explicates her desire for the construction of her own individual subjectivity. Metaphorically her stance interprets that of the then East Pakistan which vehemently opposing the oppressive hegemony of silencing struggles and at the end succeeds in constructing its own self as an independent nation.

Furthermore, the passivity of the position of Yunus Chowdhury, Safia Begum's husband during and after the Liberation War explicates both the colonial and postcolonial situations of the 'mimic men' who live the life of "a kind of non-existence, a living void" (Nesbitt 98). His inertia regarding Azad's predicament in the captivity of the Pakistani Army and even his passivity after the disappearance of Azad interpret his existential void inevitably created by the subjugation to his colonial masters.

The way Chowdhury serves the oppressive power-structure transforms him into a non-existence in postcolonial situations. Chowdhury lets the government of Pakistan use his *Custom Ford Car* for Prince Philip, a distinguished guest of the state (25). He also accompanies Prince Philip in his hunting expedition. These incidents demonstrate his affinity with the power-structure. Hence, after the independence in a newly emerged nation he only re-attires himself with his old identity and this disposition conspicuously emanates out of his inertia. Paradigm shift of the colonial power into postcolonial conditions challenges the consistency of identity, resulting in dislocation and disconnectedness and dissuades the indigenous voice-formation-process. Chowdhury also represents the hybrid postcolonial people whose “lives are distinguished by cultural clash, linguistic collision, and transnational movement” (Huddart 14). Even the alienation of Safia Begum, marked by silence and segregation from her usual community representing Jahanara Imam refers to the postcolonial cultural clash and linguistic collision, some of the chronic realities of Bangladesh which still appears to be on the developing process. This fluidity of the national identity of Bangladesh can be interpreted through the characters of both Chowdhury and Safia Begum.

Circular Structure and the Recurrent Value of the Narrative

The novel moves in a circle by opening and ending in the same funeral ceremony giving a perpetual standing of the mother's struggle all over the country. The freedom fighters like Nasir Uddin Yusuf Bacchu, Shahadat Chowdhury, Fateh Chowdhury, Habibul Alam, Raisul Islam Asad, Abul Barak Alvi, Shahidullah Khan Badal, Samad, Mahbub, Linu Billah, Hubert Rogareo and some others otherwise scattered come to a ground on the occasion of the funeral and that may be the flickers for a new beginning of fight for real freedom. Again, Jahanara Imam's position on the occasion is also significant. Even nature becomes one with all and the author's employment of pathetic fallacy, that exposure of human emotions through the elements of nature adds a new significance to the funeral scene. The congregation of all these

freedom fighters suggests how silence itself may turn into a tremendous voice, essential for fulfilling the objective of the Liberation War of Bangladesh. Though Safia Begum, after the disappearance of Azad from the custody of the Pakistani Army leads a life unheard and almost unseen, becomes tremendously powerful through her death in uniting the brave sons of the nation, whose integrity can lead the country to its desired objective, that is, justice, emancipation and democracy. Hence, the circular narrative technique aptly explicates the temporality of the nation's being and becoming by bringing about a convergent between the diachronic and the synchronic contexts of the text.

Perspective

The story is principally captured through the eyes of the freedom fighters carrying nostalgia, laments and the inquisitive mind of the author which unsettle their mind and keep the narrative open. So, the novel inevitably goes through the entanglement of historicity and simultaneously textuality of history has also added a new dimension to the text. The way the plot of the novel frequently sways between fact and fiction is tremendously engaging for the readers. A discursive synthesis between fact and fiction constructs the novel as a historicist text. True, history is an institution which should be available to the community which inherits it. Negotiation between fact and fiction creates each other's meanings and thus, there is no such thing as a private history. Anisul Hoque, like an archaeologist, seeks to account for the discursive formation of the spatiality and temporality of history and in his search Safia Begum instrumentally plays the role of a catalyst.

Being Through Denial

Safia Begum has her own form of protest within her periphery of not compromising with her position within the patriarchal society and power structure. Till the last day of her life, she sustains her denial not to yield to the imposition on the supposedly inferior section. It is customary to engrave the husband's name on the

grave wall. As one fighter against patriarchal imposition and erasure of the women's rights, Safia Begum gives clear instructions to have only one identity on the grave wall, 'The Mother of Shaheed Azad', a conscious gesture to challenge the one-sidedly imposed practice even when she is no more on earth. Her denial starts with asserting her determined position of not sharing the domestic space with any interference from anyone, and thus she comes out to oppose the commonly practiced form of polygamy among the Muslims specially the wealthy who would often marry someone much younger of their age, and marginalise the female figure who has been a dominantly helping and nurturing agent in the career of the patriarch. While Choudhury in Kanpur Engineering College was pursuing his studies, "Safia Begum provided him the financial assistance" and she "also provided him with capital to start his business" in newly created Pakistan (19). Her expectation is in exchange for her contribution made in the formation period of Mr. Choudhury, which may aptly be concomitant with Bangabandhu's demand in London on 10th January 1972 from the British to contribute to the construction of the newly independent country in exchange for our contribution in their formation period. Safia thus represents those females who voice themselves instead of keeping mute in times of adversaries positioning herself as a pioneer rebel at that juncture.

Abnegation and Emergence

By distancing herself from all the privileges, she emerges as a figure who can sacrifice everything for her cause of not budging an inch from her deserved position which she has crafted for years by standing by her man and relishing on her gain. This saintly dimension has been stressed by one coincidence. She dies on the same day exactly after 14 years on 30th August, 1984 after Azad was picked up by the Pakistan army on 30th August 1971, and "Azad never came back again" (11). By emphasizing this coincidence, the author has placed her in the tradition of the saints and great people many of whom are also said to have repeated the similar type of incidents, and this further stresses her position in

conforming to her ideal of not relenting to any fear or pressure and adopting the opposite life of a pauper leaving behind that of pelf.

Struggle through Burning the Boat

The patriarch husband keeps no openness for Safia Begum in realizing her position, and in retort and protest, she too beyond the domineering husband's farthest imagination sets closure to any negotiation in diminishing her position. Thus, she in her attempt to equate herself as the worthy mother of the freedom fighter-in-the-making determines her way not to compromise even at the cost of everything that is supposed to be counted in the life- husband, house, wealth and security, "One day she came out of Eskaton house with one dress on". This willpower not to be subservient to the dominant can be analogous to Pakistani rulers to the Bangladeshi people who despite their vulnerability and manifest incapability deny to welcome or accept the impositions and exploitations by the rulers, and has advanced on the risk space and proved it a productive and progressive ground to gain emancipation. Safia Begum is thus a figure to signify the nation itself which despite its constraints deny to dissolve into the oppressive structures the newly created state of Pakistan has given birth as it is often said, "Pakistan was created to ensure the interest of the Muslim clerks and the rising rich" (19) among whom Yusuf Choudhury was in the forefront.

Guide and Guardian in Times of Need

As a guide and guardian, Safia Begum grows to be a solver of higher calibre and can clear the mist in no time. Azad knows his position to his mother as she has no attachment or infatuation, and at the cost of everything material and mundane, she takes to austere life and brings up her only surviving child worthily with a strong sense of sacrifice for greater cause. Choosing between a secured life by being neutral and absent in the war days in the Liberation War days, and engaging himself in the riskier actions to liberate the country, he faces a dilemma, and hesitates to ask for

the mother's permission to tread the toughest but sacred path. He manages to tell his mother of his wish to join the war and later on, serves the crack platoon as a guerilla member. With every predicament to face death consequences ahead, she takes time to think over the choices and her position, and comes out with a clear direction and desire, "Have I brought you up only for me? This country is also your mother. Go ahead and come back after liberating the country." The woman who in no time denies the coexistence of a co-wife comes to place herself as a coordinate to the country itself elevating her position to the national level and equating herself to the motherland unconditionally sacrificing for greater causes. This position has been a long nurtured one as in the previous years of self-abnegation; she has always wanted to bring Azad up as a good human being in the broader sense, a good human who can sacrifice himself for greater cause. When Azad stops school, she sends her back for education as she articulates the mission of her life, "Why am I alive? To bring you up as a good human being." As a country always prepares her sons and daughters for constructive purpose of standing for the greater cause, Safia Begum too comes out to embrace that image and expand it to the necessities. The mother's guardianship expands itself to be a guardian angel and a fortress for the freedom fighters who need a safe ground for hiding themselves and their weapons. When Azad informs her of some of his friends who want to stay in her house in Mogbazar, she takes time to think over the proposal, broods over the brutality of the Pakistani Army she has come to know and the freedom fighters counter attacks, other mothers who have allowed their sons to join the war, she consents, "Bring your friends" (174) and assures them all of her open door in times of need. Consequently, "their house in Mogbazar becomes a small cantonment. Huge amount of ammunition and weapons would come to the house" (175). This position has been strengthened by her religious attachment manifested through her allegiance to the Peer Saheb of Jurain who says, "As oppression on the women has started, the Pakistani Army will not succeed. Allah will not tolerate this oppression" (174). This religious sentiment and attachment attest her to the religious attachment of the common people and

this very nature of the people has also been reflected in the historical 7th March Speech by Bangabandhu which he concludes by saying, “Blood we have sacrificed, we will sacrifice more. We won’t stop until we come out victorious” (*Translation is ours*).

Expanding Motherhood through Transcendence

The mother sustains her image by transcending the boundaries traditionally set to contain the likes of her. While she confines herself in the exercise of motherhood around the only son, she cultivates the capability to expand her motherly position to accommodate more sons and daughters without discrimination. The mother position is thus consolidated in the wider national perspectives, and she can decide on crucial issues from that elevated position. Azad has been caught and kept in on the bare floor of Ramna thana, and is tortured and tantalized to let him free if he passes information about the whereabouts of his co-fighters and their strategies. A young man brought up in elite association with hardly any physical toil or assault endures all tortures without relenting to the demand of the invading enemy as he informs his mother, “Ma, if I tell them everyone’s name, I will be released” (267). The mother, however, remains a hope to the oppressive agents for enacting the desire of eliciting information about the freedom fighters, and so she is brought to him if she coaxes the son to do damage to the fighting associates to save his own life. Contrary to the expectation of the torturers, the mother fails their motive, thwarts their mission and emerges as a strategic partner in the riskier position to strengthen the morale and advance the nationalist cause by individually sacrificing in the lived space. The freedom’s mother stresses the ultimate necessity in the historical juncture, “Babare (my son), whenever they beat you, keep yourself strong. Put up with the torture. Even by accident, don’t tell them anyone’s name” (267). This characteristic integrity outdoes the discursive onslaught of the coercion on the part of the power-structure and insists a comprehensive dismantling of the oppressive hierarchies. At this point Safia Begum transcends from an individual to a collective voice containing multitudes; from an

individual self to the collective self who, on the face of apprehension of turning into a non-being, like Walt Whitmanian ‘self’ seems to proclaim, “I am large, I contain multitudes” (351). Fourteen years’ journey of Safia Begum from the Liberation War till her death is an evolutionary process of her transformation from and individual to a collective self, an institution shared by multitudes of voices contributing to the formation of the Bangladeshi nationhood.

Finally, such transcendence ascribes to Safia Begum’s femaleness “an equal share in the making of anti-colonial subjectivity” (Gandhi 100). Her rigorous stance regarding her position against her husband and Her son Azad’s martyrdom links her with “the histories and struggles of third world women against racism, sexism, colonialism, imperialism, and monopoly capital” (Katrak 41). Her location in a divergent society marked by colonialism, capitalism, patriarchy and neo-colonial realities portrays her as a resistance against the mystification and manipulation of the history of the evolution of the nationhood of Bangladesh.

Works Cited

- Aiyar, Mani Shankar. “In The Streets of Dacca”, *Outlook*, 5 February 2022. Accessed on 30 June, 2024 at <https://www.outlookindia.com/books/in-the-streets-of-dacca-news-293394>
- Barker, Jill. “The Self, The Other and the Text: Psychoanalytic Criticism.” *Introducing Literary Theories: A Guide and Glossary*, edited by Julian Wolfreys. New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers and Distributors, 2001. pp. 98-116.
- Basha, Mahaboob and Prem Raj, Anil. “Negotiating Ethnicity and Gender Identity in Anisul Hoque’s *Freedom’s Mother* and Monica Ali’s *Brick Lane*.” *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, Volume-7, Issue-ICETESM, March 2019. pp. 95-98.
- Basha, Syed Mahaboob and Kumar, Dr. A. Phaniraja. “A Critical Study of Narrating the Culture of Resistance: Anisul

- Huque's *Freedoms Mother*", *Research Journal of English Language and Literature (RJELAL)*. Vol. 10, Issue 1, 2022 (Jan-Mar). pp. 265-267.
- Chakravorty, Bhaswati. "Birth Pangs", *Biblio*, April 2012. p. 18.
- Das, Chaity. "The Aesthetic of Freedom: Fiction of and in Times of Siege", *In the Land of Buried Tongues: Testimonies and Literary Narratives of the War of Liberation of Bangladesh*, Delhi, Oxford Academic, 2017. pp. 192-248.
- Das, Srijana Mitra. "Allow history to settle down", *Times of India*, 26 March, 2012. p. 10.
- Greenblatt, Stephen. "The Circulation of Social Energy". *Modern Criticism and Theory: A Reader*, edited by David Lodge. Longman, 2000. pp. 495-511.
- Hawthorn, Jeremy. *A Glossary of Contemporary Theory*. UK: Arnold, 2000.
- Hoque, Anisul. *Maa*. Shomoy, 2020.
- Huddart, David. *Postcolonial Theory and Autobiography*. Routledge, 2008.
- Katrak, Ketu H. *Politics of the Female Body: Postcolonial Women Writers of the Third World*. New Jersey: Rutgers University Press, 2006.
- Khan, Heena. "Love and Loss", *Hindu Business Line*, p.8. Delhi, 13 July, 2012.
- Khan, Nahid. "The tears and pride of a mother", *The Daily Star*, May 28, 2011. Access at <https://www.thedailystar.net/news-detail-187486>
- Leela, Gandhi. *Postcolonial Theory: A Critical Introduction*. London: Oxford University Press, 1998.
- Nesbitt, L. "Identity in a Postcolonial Void". *Postcolonial Identities*, edited by Smith and Ce[ed]. Handel, 2014. pp. 98-112.
- Parvin, Shahnaz. "War Mothers in a Non-Fiction and Two Fictional Works on the Liberation War of Bangladesh". *Bangladesh Research Foundation*, Vol. 4. No. 2. June 2015. pp. 113-119.
- Rushdie, Salman. *Languages of Truth: Essays 2003-2020*. New York: Random House, 2021.

Whitman, Walt. *Leaves of Grass*. California: Sea Wolf Press, 2023.